

PROSPECTS OF IMPLEMENTING INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT PROGRAMS IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Annotation: This article focuses on the introduction of international assessment programs in Primary Education, Foreign experience in improving literacy of Primary School students, International Assessment Program PIRLS (progress in international reading and literacy study), which is currently considered one of the most pressing issues.

Keywords: PISA, PIRLIS, TIMSS, ICILS, International Assessment Program, National Education System, primary education.

Today, at a time when our country is rapidly developing on the path of innovative development, it is necessary to comprehensively support the creative ideas and creativity of young people, to form their knowledge, skills and qualifications, as well as advanced foreign experiences, international standards and requirements. It is important to improve the assessment system based on this, to study international experiences, to conduct a comprehensive comparative analysis of the existing system, to closely cooperate with relevant international and foreign organizations and scientific research institutions.

In order to implement these tasks, the implementation of the international assessment program in our country for the assessment of the knowledge of primary school students, participation in the Ministry-level conference on the topic of using experiences: problems and solutions has a special place. Therefore, it is necessary to provide information for the employees of the public education system, teachers and those interested in the field of education about new international studies in the field of education, as well as about the prospects of introducing the International Assessment Program. is appropriate

Enlightenment scholar Abdulla Avloni said hundreds of years ago, "*Education is a matter of life - or death, or salvation - or destruction, or happiness - or disaster*" - has not lost its value even today. In fact, the education of our youth is very important for us to be enriched with the world. Of course, from the first years of independence, great attention was paid to the reform of the education system in

our country, and certain achievements have been made in this field. In the continuing education system, in particular, preschool education, general secondary education, secondary special education, vocational education, higher education, professional development and retraining, extracurricular education great changes have taken place in the species. But in the era of globalization, it cannot be overlooked that science, technology and technology are rapidly developing in the world. This, in turn, puts new demands on education and science. Regular reform of the education system, improvement of modern methods and means of teaching, enrichment of the content of education remains an urgent requirement of today. Naturally, when we think about the introduction of international assessment programs in primary education, we all have a legitimate question:

What is the importance of international assessment programs?

What International Assessment Programs Are Available?

What does participation in international studies on the assessment of the quality of education give to Uzbekistan?

We can cite several essential importance of international evaluation program today.

As a result of the reforms carried out in our country in recent years, huge economic growth indicators are being achieved, increasing the demand for qualified personnel and advanced specialists in all fields. This in itself requires increasing the interest of our students in lessons and increasing the attention of teachers to all-round education.

The fact that the above requirements are very important for the educational system means that, as in most foreign countries, it is necessary to attract the best practices aimed at improving the quality of education by evaluating and monitoring the development of the educational and scientific fields.

Today, there are the following international assessment programs that serve to determine the level of knowledge of students:

PISA is an international program for assessing the educational achievements of students

PIRLS is an international study that determines the level of reading and comprehension of text

TIMSS is an international monitoring of the quality of mathematics and science at school

There are a number of international programs, such as ICILS - International Research on Computer and Information Literacy, which are widely used as a criterion for improving the quality of education in developed countries.

PISA (English - Program for International Student Assessment) is a program that assesses literacy (reading, mathematics, natural sciences) and the ability to apply knowledge of 15-year-old students in different countries. This program is held once every 3 years. It was originally developed in 1997 and was first used in 2000.

A 50-point increase in the PISA score provides a 1% increase in annual gross domestic product (GDP).

In PISA, monitoring of the quality of students' knowledge is determined in 5 areas.

- ❖ *Reading literacy;*
- ❖ *Mathematical literacy;*
- ❖ *Financial literacy;*
- ❖ *Computer literacy;*
- ❖ *Natural and scientific literacy.*

Uzbekistan is expected to participate in 3 directions (reading literacy, mathematical literacy, natural and scientific literacy) in 2021.

PIRLS- (English - Progress in International Reading Literacy Study - an international study that determines the level of reading and understanding of the text) the purpose of this international study is to study the reading and It consists of identifying and evaluating the specific characteristics of the educational system that lead to the readiness for reception and the achievement of different students. Of course, such research is of great importance for workers in the field of public education, scientists, methodologists, teachers, parents and public representatives. PIRLS research is coordinated by the International Association of Educational Institutions (IEA). It was organized by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA-International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement). All responsibility for the organization of the international research is assigned to the Boston College of Chestnut Hill (Maccachucetc, USA). The preparation of tasks for the research is carried out in the German (Hamburg) data center. The first research was conducted in 2001. The research is conducted every 5 years. It is held several times. In different countries participating in the PIRLS study, the age of admission to primary school varies. In many countries, they enter school at the age of six and finish the fourth grade at the age of 10.5 years. However, in England, New Zealand, Trinidad and Tobago - they enter school at the age of 5, and the important point is that in the PIRLS international study, the 5th graders of these countries participated in the international study. In Sweden, Denmark and many Eastern countries, admission to school starts at the age of 7, and the

students of these countries have the highest age (10.7-10.9) compared to the rest of their peers.

TIMSS (Trends in International mathematics and science study) is a program for assessing the level of mastery of mathematics and natural sciences of 4th and 8th grade students, and this research is conducted once every four years.

In addition to comparing the level and quality of knowledge acquired by 4th and 8th grade students in mathematics and natural sciences in the TIMSS international assessment program, as well as identifying differences in the national education system, in addition, the content of education in mathematics and natural sciences in schools, the educational process, the capabilities of the educational institution, the potential of teachers, factors related to students' families are studied.

The TIMSS program launched its first survey in 1995 and has been conducted every four years until 2019 in 1999, 2003, 2007, 2011, 2015 and 2019. The next 8th cycle is planned to be implemented in 2023.

The number of countries participating in the program is also steadily increasing, as can be seen from the 2015 TIMSS study, when 57 countries participated, and in 2019, this number increased to more than 60 countries. According to the results of the TIMSS 2015 study, the educational system of countries such as the USA, Singapore, Hong Kong, the Republic of Korea, Japan, Russia, and Great Britain have the highest indicators.

ICILS (International Computer Information Literacy Study) - International Computer and Information Literacy Study evaluates the knowledge of information and communication technologies of students and teachers around the world. This test was created by the International Association for the Assessment of Educational Achievement in June 2010.

What does participation in international studies on the assessment of the quality of education give to Uzbekistan?

It is used to reform the national education system, improve the content of education, training and professional development programs for pedagogues, and create a new generation of textbooks by experts. The results obtained in the research allow us to draw conclusions about the quality of education in the country and its place taking into account international standards. *And international studies:*

- has a positive effect on the quality of national research in the field of education.
- allows to create a national evaluation system based on high economic efficiency at the level of international standards.

- allows to create a national evaluation system based on high economic efficiency at the level of international standards.
- By participating in international research involving the leading experts of various organizations in Uzbekistan, the culture of monitoring research will be developed among our local experts, and it will lead to the adaptation of education quality assessment to international standards.
- -Enables the development of control materials for assessing the quality of national education at the level of the quality of control materials used in international studies.

I would like to present my comments and suggestions on the topic "Prospects for the introduction of international assessment programs in primary education". In order to do well in an international assessment program, you need to have at least 2 goals:

The first is the preparation of teachers and the materials they will work with. After all, it is not for nothing that international studies say that the quality of education in schools depends on the professional level of teachers. Therefore, it is necessary to allocate funds for the training of teachers and create new educational materials. Relevant ministries should create conditions for investment, financing and methodological support in the training system.

Second, in order to improve the results in international studies, it is necessary to train teachers in a targeted way and change the teaching methodology and priority principles in the educational process. It is necessary to provide materials that can be used more successfully in the educational process.

In short, this program will serve to further increase the intellectual potential of our country's youth.

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